

COMPARATIVE EFFECTIVENESS OF PROSTHETICS WITH CLASP AND PARTIALLY REMOVABLE LAMELLAR DENTURES

Gurskaya N.

*Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant
Department of Orthopedic Dentistry*

Rustamov E.

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Demirchiyeva M.

Doctor of Philosophy in Medicine, Assistant

Department of Therapeutic Dentistry

Azerbaijan Medical University

Baku, Azerbaijan

Abstract

Clasp dentures have become widespread due to the widespread introduction of casting technology for various metal alloys into dental institutions. These prostheses differ significantly in design and method of distributing the load on supporting tissues from other prostheses used to eliminate defects in the dentition. They rest on the teeth and the toothless area of the alveolar process or alveolar part. At the same time, they transmit chewing pressure to two biologically different structures: the periodontium of the supporting teeth and the mucous membrane of the alveolar ridge.

Keywords: partial loss of teeth, clasp dentures, plate dentures.

The purpose of the study is to increase the effectiveness of orthopedic treatment using various designs of removable dentures in patients with partial absence of teeth.

Material and methods. A total of 20 patients with partial absence of teeth were examined and received orthopedic treatment during the year. Depending on the orthopedic treatment plan, two groups of patients were identified. In the 1st group (n=10) clasp dentures with a clasp fixation system were made, and in the 2nd group (n=10) partial removable laminar dentures with wire retaining clasps were made. The criteria for inclusion of patients in the study were: partial absence of teeth, indications for removable dentures, absence of somatic diseases in the acute stage, diseases of the mucous membrane [1.2.3]. To assess the severity of inflammation of the soft tissues and the state of epithelization of the prosthetic bed, a Schiller test was performed, modified by Yu. Pisarev, by treating the oral mucosa with a potassium iodide solution [4.5.6]. To assess the subjective feelings of patients when using partial removable dentures, a questionnaire was used, in which the patient, answering five questions, ranked the answer in points from 1 to 5 [7.8]. The questions concerned the assessment of the restoration of five functions: 1. Restoration of chewing function; 2. Restoration of the act of swallowing; 3. No pain associated with the prosthesis in the oral cavity; 4. Restoration of diction; 5. Restoration of salivation. With a total score of 18 or more, the result was considered good; from 14 to 17 points - satisfactory; 13 points or less - unsatisfactory

Results.

Thus, in patients of group 1, moderate inflammation predominated before prosthetics and after 3 months, 69 and 85%, respectively. After 6 months, the indicators improved towards mild inflammation and amounted to 93%. Group 2 patients were characterized by moderate inflammation throughout the study. Thus, the highest rates were after 6 months - 85%. After 6 months they decreased to 82%, but still remained at an

elevated level. In group 1, patients noted shorter periods and higher quality of restoration of chewing function, swallowing, diction, salivation, and also experienced less pain associated with the use of dentures in less quantity and intensity. From this we can conclude that the scoring of the effectiveness of prostheses, taking into account subjective sensations, in patients of group 2 compared with group 1 was lower in the immediate period after prosthetics by 14%, after 3 months - by 15%, after 6 months - by 22%. A comparative analysis of the data obtained revealed that when patients with dentition defects used partial removable laminar dentures compared to clasp dentures, the performance parameters of orthopedic structures were objectively lower. When patients were fitted with partial removable plate dentures, chewing efficiency was lower—chewing time was prolonged, the quality of grinding solid food was reduced, and the adaptation period of getting used to the dentures was lengthened. From the above data we can conclude that when providing prosthetics for patients with partial absence of teeth, clasp dentures function with greater efficiency compared to partial removable plate dentures in almost all evaluation parameters. This circumstance allows us to recommend clasp dentures for prosthetics of patients in the treatment of dentition defects.

Conclusion.

In total, 20 patients with partial absence of teeth were examined and received orthopedic treatment and 2 groups were identified: in one, clasp dentures were made, in the second, partial removable laminar dentures were made. In the immediate period after prosthetics, as well as 3 and 6 months after orthopedic treatment, the condition of the supporting teeth and tissues of the prosthetic bed was examined. Thus, the work established that when providing prosthetics for patients with dentition defects, partial removable lamellar dentures have a more pronounced effect on the tissues of the prosthetic bed and supporting teeth than clasp dentures. Moderate inflammation predominated (82%),

with intense inflammation of the gums present in 7.5%. Moderate gingivitis predominated (75%), with severe gingivitis present in 13.4%. The average degree of inflammatory-destructive processes in the periodontium predominated (78%). When assessing the effectiveness of prosthetics for partial loss of teeth, patients with clasp dentures noted that the quality of restoration of chewing function, swallowing, diction, and the normal volume of salivation was higher, and the recovery time was lower; in addition, they experienced less pain associated with the use of dentures: through 6 months chewing efficiency is lower in group 2 (56% versus 84%) by 27%; The score for the effectiveness of partial removable dentures, taking into account subjective sensations, is also lower than the 2nd group after 6 months - by 22%. Thus, the conducted study of the results of orthopedic treatment of patients with partial absence of teeth indicates the advantage of using clasp dentures over partial removable laminar dentures, based on the condition of periodontal tissues, the prosthetic bed, the results of functional tests and a qualitative assessment of the results of the operation of the dentures and the level of dental health.

References

1. Maksjukov S.Ju., Belikova E.S., Gadzhieva D.N., Shahbazov O.I. Sovremennoe sostojanie problemy srokov sluzhby i jekspluatacii protezov, garantijnyh srokov pri povtornom protezirovanii // Glavnyj vrach Juga Rossii. -2012 (maj). - S. 17-20.
2. Vul'fes H. Sovremennye tehnologii protezirovanija. M.: Academia dental. 467.
3. Dzhepson N. Chastichnye s#emnye protezy. M.: MEDpress; 2006.
4. Zhulev E.N. Chastichnye s#emnye protezy (teorija, klinika i laboratornaja tehnika). Nizhnij Novgorod.: Nizhegorodskaja gosudarstvennaja medicinskaja akademija; 2000.
5. Zagorskij V.A. Chastichnye s#emnye i perekryvajushhie protezy. M.: Medicina; 2007.
6. Kopejkin V.N., Mirgazizov M.Z., Malyj A.Ju. Oshibki v ortopedicheskoj stomatologii: Professional'nye i mediko-pravovye aspekty. M. 2002.
7. Kopejkin V.N., Mirgazizov M.Z. Ortopedicheskaja stomatologija. M. 2001.
8. Arigbede AO, Dosumu OO, Esan TA, Akeredolu PA. Acceptability of maxillary major connectors in removable partial dentures. Afr Health Science. 2006;6:2:113-117.